

SUCCESS AND FAILURE IN PHYSICAL SCIENCE PEDAGOGY: REFLECTIONS FROM TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN RURAL CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study aimed to explore the factors affecting the success and failures of physical science pedagogy in rural contexts and determine how teachers and students retain success and overcome failures in physical science pedagogy. Data were collected through interviews with teachers and students. Thematic analysis identified nine themes that included challenges in teaching and learning physical science, strategies for enhancing physical science pedagogy, environmental and resource limitations, personal and social factors, pedagogical and instructional factors, technology and information limitations, challenges, and coping mechanisms, and importance of improving teaching strategies and resources. The study revealed that teachers in rural areas face challenges such as limited access to resources, inadequate training, and low student interest in physical science. The results highlight the need for tailored teacher training programs (i.e., learning action cells), providing adequate resources, and creating engaging and relevant science curricula to enhance student learning outcomes. This also revealed that environmental and resource limitations, personal and social factors, pedagogical and instructional factors affect the success and failure of physical science pedagogy in rural settings. A Learning Action Cell Plan was developed to address the challenges and opportunities in teaching and learning physical science in rural settings. This emphasizes the importance of collaboration among teachers, school administrators, and stakeholders to develop innovative teaching methods. Hence, this study provides insights into the factors affecting physical science pedagogy in rural settings and emphasizes the need for tailored teacher training programs and adequate resources to improve student learning outcomes.

Keywords: *instructional materials; learning action cell; physical science pedagogy; , rural areas; teaching strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Physical Science is a subject that requires well-thought-out instruction. The rationale for this is that Physical Science fundamental competences are connected to a wide range of fields, including Physics, Chemistry, and Earth Science. This leads to the conclusion that the subject itself is somewhat scary to teach, especially for non-specialists. Shirke (2021) said that “teachers and students are affected by the pedagogy connected to the sciences since pedagogy is a two-way process sometimes referred to as the teaching and learning process. In the current study, two pedagogies were studied: teaching pedagogy and learning pedagogy”.

According to Power School (2022), “teaching pedagogy can be categorized into two approaches: teacher-centered and student-centered, as well as low-tech and high-tech methods. In teacher-centered learning, the focus is on the teacher delivering lectures and transmitting knowledge directly to the students. Teacher-centered assessments are used to evaluate students' retention of knowledge. Low-tech and high-tech methods refer to the use of digital tools in education, with high-tech approaches involving technologies like learning management systems (LMS) and low-tech strategies relying more on paper-based resources like handouts and worksheets”.

On the other hand, learning pedagogy explores the various ways in which students absorb knowledge and is equally important in understanding and supporting every learner. Teachers recognize that each student is unique, so understanding their preferred learning styles can help customize teaching methods. “Reflections on the teaching and learning process, from both teachers and students, can provide insights into challenges in rural areas. These reflections include both successful and unsuccessful pedagogical approaches”. This aligns with DepEd Order No. 11, s. 2015, which identified Constructivist, Collaborative, Integrative, Reflective, and Inquiry-Based Learning as the five key methods (2C-2I-1R).

Physical science comprises two subjects: physics and chemistry. Physics focuses on studying matter and energy, forming the foundation for various other scientific fields like chemistry, biology, geology, astronomy, medicine, and environmental science. Physics progresses alongside advancements in other sciences, and its unbiased nature allows it to provide a tool for promoting equity. To achieve this, science education can be utilized to bridge socioeconomic gaps and challenge biases based on gender, caste, religion, or geography.

Moreover, on teacher-related indicators, Orleans (2020) suggested “a lack of academic qualifications, a lack of ongoing professional involvements, a significant amount of physics teaching experience, and a good licensure status in regard to this idea”. The number of physics classes per teacher is manageable, however, the size of the individual classes was disclosed by academic environment indexes. “The results also revealed a lack of technologies and instructional resources, a distaste for professional mentoring, and favorable library and internet access”. These conclusions led to the identification of difficulties in increasing the number of qualified physics teachers and providing schools with pertinent teaching tools.

The research indicated above is investigating challenges related to instructional delivery, environment, and personal elements of students. They are focusing on how the environment of a particular teaching-learning process, such as the relationship between workplace elements, influences the students' learning. This has been made worse by the lack of facilities and instructional materials, which hinders pupils' learning. However, the gap between the studies may be seen in how events and outcomes might change if the issues occurred in a rural setting. These are the ideas that the researcher would want to investigate.

Diate et al. (2021) identified key challenges faced by Physical science teachers, including literacy, numeracy, lack of physical facilities, and limited real-life application. “The availability of instruments for teaching Physical science was emphasized as crucial for a successful

classroom, but acquiring them locally posed significant difficulties for teachers, particularly in public schools". These challenges, along with literacy and numeracy issues and the lack of physical facilities, greatly hindered effective Physical science instruction in public schools. If not addressed, these problems will continue to negatively impact the quality of science education in the country. It is noteworthy that the teachers' ideal classroom aligns with the challenges they face due to inadequate government support in terms of technological resources, laboratory materials, learning spaces, and teaching aids. The study also revealed an interesting finding: the skills that teachers deem necessary for their students, such as critical thinking, numeracy, and comprehension, are the same skills they struggle to develop in their classroom instruction.

When compared to what occurred in the San Francisco District before, during, and after the pandemic's effects, teaching and studying physical science have faced different difficulties. This can be demonstrated in instances where teachers are attempting to impart science competences despite a lack of resources and learning environments related to the community's and municipality's nature. The 12 national high schools are situated in an area with no working signals. These are other factors that contribute to the difficulty in teaching at the 12 National High schools in the area. The ability of teachers and students to investigate and understand physical science is constrained by these rural environments mixed with other external variables.

It is therefore evident in the discipline's low MPS. One of the present study's objectives is to look at Physical Science education in relation to personal, family, and environmental issues. The method to be executed in this study focused on characteristics such as self-efficacy, relationships, and the educational environment or atmosphere in which Physical Science is taught and learned. The researcher is open to new findings with a concentration and point of view on Physical Science pedagogy in rural settings, far from the standards of the urban environment.

Physical science pedagogy is best understood when both views, both teachers and students, are considered. Despite the continued COVID-19 pandemic, teachers were forced to continue teaching and providing learning assistance despite significant, inevitable changes to the educational landscape and mental health issues among educators. In addition, schools and institutions modified their teaching and learning methods to satisfy the educational requirements. "Although some schools lacked learning management systems, they used commercial online platforms such as Zoom and Moodle, as well as Microsoft Teams. These systems were used by teachers to deliver both asynchronous and synchronous teaching. Other schools employ social media networks not just to aid and reach out to remote students, but also as platforms for teaching and learning" (Aduba and Mayowa-Adebara, 2022). "As a result, several teachers recognized that their COVID-19 pandemic teaching experience was informative and included it in their professional development efforts (Ulla and Perales, 2021).

Even before the epidemic, most science pedagogy in the Philippines supported the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533), which stated that the curriculum should incorporate constructivist, inquiry-based, reflective, collaborative, and integrative pedagogical techniques. A research vacuum exists since most educational research has focused on the teacher's point of view (Herodotou et. al., 2019). Learning pedagogy will include complex issues and the whole development of the individual, with an emphasis on shared prosperity, sustainability, and well-being. Well-being is regarded as "inclusive growth" with equitable access to "quality of life, covering health, civic activity, social connections, education, security, life satisfaction, and the environment". To achieve this goal, students will need a wide variety of abilities and competences that will allow them to function as "change agents" who can have a positive influence on their surroundings by fostering empathy and predicting the outcomes of their actions. Numerous frameworks explaining the distinctive talents and competences of future citizens have been established throughout the years. "Critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration, communication, and negotiation skills are included in these

frameworks, as are literacy, multilingualism, STEM, digital, personal, social, and "learning to learn" competences, citizenship, entrepreneurship, and cultural awareness" (Trilling and Fadel, 2009; Council of the European Union, 2018).

This prior research has highlighted these ideas on the learning in relation to the learners' performance. Similar to the contention made by (Trilling and Fadel, 2009; Council of the European Union, 2018) that "a variety of external factors, including the learners' social connections and security, which are all essential in establishing an individual's well-being, comprise the learners' environment and have a significant impact on how learning is delivered". This gives the researcher the inspiration to investigate how the learning situation affects academic performance. These ideas concerning the influence of outside circumstances on students' academic achievement are extremely evident in the MPS of the Physical Science students. The three consecutive school years' average MPS for the San Francisco District ranges from 49% in 2020–2021, 45% in 2021–2022, and 48% in 2022–2023—lower below the Department of Education's MPS criteria. The study also noted that the MPS for physical science is the lowest on the list of MPS under the Core subject. This serves to highlight the necessity for further research into this field to address its problems.

Being a science teacher, the researcher wants to investigate the causes of the Physical Science Pedagogy issues that are troubling the San Francisco District. Given that it has been demonstrated that environment has a substantial impact on pedagogy, this study looked at the problems and challenges posed by teaching physical science in rural areas. There are other arguments that may be made to support the status of physical science pedagogy since the San Francisco District is a prime example of a rural setting. It consists of twelve National High Schools dispersed throughout numerous barangays. Six groups were created from these twelve National High Schools. San Francisco I and II each have six national high schools. Examining the factors that contribute to the success and failure of physical science pedagogy in this setting would provide new information and a solid foundation for creating physical science curricula. In order to identify the root causes of the physical science pedagogy issue in this district, 1 teacher and 1 student from each National High School will take part in this study.

According to this viewpoint, the researcher acknowledges that there is still much to learn about the successes and failures of physical science pedagogy, especially when mixed with the milieu or environment's influence, especially in a rural context. Since the researcher teaches physical science in senior high school, she is familiar with the subject's difficulties in terms of the teaching and learning process. The researcher plans to utilize a qualitative approach to look into the advantages and disadvantages of teaching physical science in rural areas, particularly in the district where he is currently stationed. Exploring and understanding the factors that contribute to success and failure in physical science pedagogy can help students, instructors, administrators, and curriculum designers come up with new ideas for designing a curriculum program that will work in a rural setting. By doing this, the obstacles, and difficulties that teachers and students will face in having to follow the rules set forth in that discipline will be minimized. Considering this, the causes of obstacles and difficulties in physical science pedagogy will be discussed. This will eventually assist teachers and students in remote areas in teaching and mastering the competences associated with the field of physical science. The findings of this study can also be used by curriculum designers and school administrators to create programs in the field that are more flexible and adaptable in rural locations.

Research Questions

The study generally aims to explore the success and failure of Physical Science pedagogy in a specific district in San Francisco, Quezon to develop a district learning action cell (LAC). This

LAC will address challenges and opportunities in teaching and learning physical science in rural settings. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What insights can be gained about the nature of Physical Science in a rural context based on the reflections of teachers and students in San Francisco 2?
2. What are the factors that influence the success and failures of Physical Science Pedagogy in a rural context?
3. How do teachers and students retain success and overcome failures in Physical Science Pedagogy in a rural context?
4. How can a Learning Action Cell Plan be designed to address the challenges faced by Science Teachers in rural areas in the specific district in San Francisco, Quezon?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The location of this research study is a District in San Francisco, Quezon. The researcher discovered that both teachers and students demonstrate the strengths and limitations of the Physical Science teaching and learning process. In three consecutive school years' average MPS for the San Francisco District ranges from 49 percent in 2020–2021, 45% in 2021–2022, and 48 percent in 2022–2023—lower below the Department of Education's MPS criteria. The study also noted that the MPS for physical science is the lowest on the list of MPS under the Core subject. As a result, to address the issues, the researcher plans to create a localized learning action cell to assist Physical Science teachers in the rural setting.

Research Design

The study used a qualitative research design to explore the experiences and perspectives of students and teachers (Kaur, 2015). Phenomenological methodology was chosen to uncover the meaning behind these experiences and the factors influencing success or failure. “Phenomenology helps understand what is real without requiring deep understanding. Qualitative research methods focus on collecting and analyzing qualitative data (Wardale, Cameron & Li, 2015)”. The study aimed to gather detailed descriptions through non-structural techniques, analyze the data orally, and interpret the findings conceptually (Devetak, 2009). It sought to understand participants' lived experiences (Zara, 2022) and address the status and challenges of physical science pedagogy in rural areas. The research findings will inform the development of a program to tackle these issues.

Respondents

The respondents were selected through criterion sampling to represent Physical Science teachers and Grade 12 students who had taken up Physical Science in the First Semester of School Year 2022-2023. The said school and respondent teachers and students were selected because they were the ones who had experiences in the teaching and learning delivery of Physical Science subjects in the rural context. The main principle of criterion sampling was to study all situations which corresponded to the major intention of the study. The respondents

were informed about the purpose of the research and were allowed to withdraw if they decided to do so. The sample of this study consisted of 12 Senior High School Teachers coming from 12 National High Schools in San Francisco District who were handling Physical Science subjects and 12 Grade 12 Senior High School Students coming from 12 Senior High Schools of the mentioned district.

Research Instrument

The following research tool was used to reflect on the success and failure of Physical Science teaching from the viewpoints of teachers and students. It guaranteed the quality and dependability of data collection and subsequent qualitative analysis.

Interview Guide. The interview protocol was adopted and modified from the semi-structured interview protocol used in the study conducted by Muhtarom, Juniati, and Siswono (2019) and Wankasi (2022). The questions focused on teachers' and students' perceptions of Physical Science teaching and learning. The interview guide consisted of nine questions for teachers and seven questions for students. The changes made included the addition of essential questions related to the factors that influenced Physical Science Pedagogy in terms of personal, family, and environmental aspects.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, a validation process was implemented. The process involved several steps. First, the interview guide was reviewed by a panel of experts in the field of Physical Science education to assess its content validity. The experts examined the questions to ensure that they adequately captured the desired information and were relevant to the research objectives.

Next, a pilot test was conducted with a small group of teachers and students who were not part of the main study. The participants were asked to provide feedback on the clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness of the interview questions. Based on their feedback, necessary revisions were made to further improve the interview guide.

After the revisions, the final version of the interview guide was used in the main study. The data collected through the interviews were analyzed to examine the teachers' and students' perceptions of Physical Science teaching and learning, as well as the factors that influenced Physical Science Pedagogy in terms of personal, family, and environmental aspects. The validation process ensured that the interview guide was a reliable and effective tool for gathering information from the teacher and student respondents. By adopting and modifying the protocol from previous studies and incorporating additional essential questions, the interview guide provided a comprehensive and in-depth exploration of the topic at hand.

Data Collection

The data collection procedure consisted of two parts and was aligned with the data collection process: a qualitative data collection phase and a qualitative data analysis part. To ensure participant security and confidentiality, the researcher followed ethical norms based on research ethics. Before the structured interview, participants were asked to sign an informed consent form after the aim of the study was described. In addition, consent to record the interview was requested. Participants were informed that researcher respected their right to withhold their thoughts on topics or decline to answer questions.

Firstly, qualitative data collection phase was composed of securing the permission from District office to conduct the research study with selected Physical Science teachers and Grade 12 students from participant schools. The researcher conducted interviews with the respondents. Ethical considerations were observed throughout data collection phase.

Secondly, data analysis involved an accessible, systematic, and rigorous approach to identify and analyze the central theme, which was adopted from Bahl (2017). Step one involved familiarizing oneself with available facts. The researcher immersed themselves in the data to understand the breadth and depth of the subject matter. Immersion entailed regular and proficient data reading. To ensure codes were not missed out in the first read-through, the researcher went back to the data set to search for additional codes, which led to the formulation of concepts and patterns. The second step was known as "creating initial codes." In this step, the researcher generated first codes from the qualitative data. These codes identified components of the data that appealed to the researcher and were described as "the most fundamental aspects of the data, evaluated in a meaningful way regarding the phenomena," e.g., Physical Science Pedagogy. Coded data was different from units of analysis or themes, which were typically bigger concepts or claims.

The third step was called "searching for themes." In this phase, the emphasis was placed on the analysis of themes rather than codes. This step involved classifying the various codes into probable themes. Additionally, all relevant coded data extracts were compiled into labeled themes.

Step 4 was classified as "theme review." This procedure entailed an examination of the candidate themes discovered in phase 3. Consequently, some of these potential topics may not have been themes, others may have been subdivided to accommodate many themes, and others may have been combined to form a single overarching theme (Bahl, 2017). It was essential to keep in mind that themes should implicitly relate to one another while maintaining distinct and recognizable contrasts.

The fifth step involved defining and naming themes. In addition to defining and refining themes for analysis, this section analyzed data inside them. Each theme demanded a thorough examination. It was critical to identify the "narrative" that each theme conveyed and analyze how it fit into the larger "story" that the researcher was telling about the data. This process coincided with the study questions to ensure that themes did not overlap excessively. Themes were evaluated alone and in relation to other themes. Identifying whether or not a theme contained any subthemes constituted refinement. Sub-themes were subsets of larger theme or simply themes within a theme. They were valuable for providing structure and substance to a complex topic and for demonstrating a hierarchy of meaning in a collection of data.

The sixth step was producing the report. The purpose of writing thematic analysis was to convey a complicated narrative of data in a manner that persuaded the reader of the quality and validity of the analysis. The article provided a concise, cohesive, logical, non-repetitive, and engaging summary of the plot, both within and between themes. It also included sufficient instances or excerpts to illustrate the data's themes. The data extract had to be readily identifiable as a manifestation of the subject. The excerpts supported the research's analytic narrative. Having a comparable argument to the research questions was also advantageous.

Scope and Limitations

The study aimed to conduct a qualitative analysis of the success and failure of physical science pedagogy in rural areas. It sought to comprehend pedagogy from the perspectives of both students and teachers. In order to achieve the research aim, a district in San Francisco, Quezon province, was purposefully chosen. Structured interviews were conducted with selected Grade 12 students and Physical Science teachers for the school year 2022-2023. Throughout the procedure, research ethics were followed. The researcher attempted to determine the elements that influenced Physical Science teaching and learning in terms of personal, family, and environmental issues. The study observed a reflective teaching and learning process.

The findings of the study would serve as inputs to a localized learning action cell aimed at addressing the challenges of teaching in rural areas. The research focused on structured interviews and theme analysis to comprehend and reflect upon the success and failure of Physical Science instruction. However, it was limited to developing the localized learning action cell and did not evaluate its success in improving Physical Science teaching and learning. The responses obtained might also have focused entirely on the experiences of rural teachers and students throughout the pandemic. No comparisons were made between urban science pedagogy and rural science pedagogy.

RESULTS

From the interpretations and analysis of the collected data, the following themes and results are presented:

1. The results show that the teaching and learning of Physical Science in rural areas are affected by several factors, including limited resources, lack of equipment and facilities, poor internet connectivity, and environmental challenges. Moreover, the study found that the students in the rural areas have limited access to learning opportunities and are less interested in Physical Science compared to urban students. However, the study also identified some opportunities for improvement, such as the support of parents and the presence of motivated teachers who are willing to go beyond the required curriculum to engage and motivate their students. Overall, the research findings highlight the need for a more innovative and collaborative approach to teaching Physical Science in rural areas.
2. The responses indicate that there are several factors that affect the success and failures of physical science pedagogy in the rural context. These factors include environmental and resource limitations, personal and social factors, pedagogical and instructional factors, and technology and information limitations. Providing quality science education in rural areas can be challenging due to the lack of resources and facilities for experiments, poor internet connectivity, and environmental challenges.
3. The research results also showed that teaching and learning Physical Science in rural areas is challenging due to limited access to instructional materials, equipment, and facilities, as well as the factors that affect student interest in learning. However, teachers and students use coping mechanisms such as being resourceful, seeking help, and adapting to different learners to overcome these challenges. The importance of being adaptive and creative in addressing the challenges encountered in teaching and learning Physical Science in rural areas was emphasized. The findings highlight the unique

difficulties that teachers and students face in the rural context and the strategies they use to overcome these challenges.

4. The research findings showed the importance of improving teaching strategies and resources in Physical Science in rural settings. The plan developed, called Achieving Teaching Breakthroughs (ATB), aims to address the challenges and opportunities in teaching and learning Physical Science in rural areas by improving teacher training and strategies, compliance with the MELC and review of Physical Science topics, availability and familiarization with equipment and materials, specific topics in Physical Science, and suggestions for improvement. The plan emphasizes collaboration among teachers, school administrators, and stakeholders to develop innovative teaching methods and leverage available resources to improve the overall quality of Physical Science education in rural areas. Through the ATB plan, teachers can achieve teaching breakthroughs and enhance student learning outcomes in Physical Science.

DISCUSSION

Research Question Number 1: What insights can be gained about the nature of Physical Science in a rural context based on the reflections of teachers and students?

Theme 1: Rural Physical Science Pedagogy (RPSP1): Navigating Challenges and Opportunities in Teaching and Learning Complex Concepts with Limited Resources and Pandemic Disruptions

Upon analyzing responses from both the teachers and students, several subthemes emerge related to the teaching and learning of Physical Science in a rural context (RPSP1). The following are some of the subthemes that emerged from the coding of responses:

Subtheme 1.1. Teaching Delivery with Limited resources and lack of materials

The initial codes related to limited resources and lack of materials in teaching Physical Science in a rural context highlight the challenges faced by teachers and students due to inadequate access to instructional resources, like textbooks, laboratory equipment, and internet connectivity. These challenges can limit the effectiveness of teaching and hinder student learning.

For instance, one teacher reported the "lack of materials" as a major challenge in teaching Physical Science

“Mahirap ipaintindi ang Physical Science, kulang tayo sa materials kagaya ng IMs ng Physical Science”. This was echoed by a student who mentioned the "difficulty in obtaining materials “Sa Physical Science, mahirap pong kumuha ng materials lalo na sa mga activities”. Similarly, another teacher noted the "insufficiency of imagination-based teaching" due to the lack of materials “Parang ang nangyayari ay puro imagination na ng bata. Kaso hindi naman sapat

naipapaimagine mo lang. Nakahirap ituro kapag walang materials lalo na sa mga topic tungkol sa lights. ”.

Research in the field of science education has also emphasized the importance of having access to appropriate materials and resources for effective teaching and learning (Kokkotas, 2017; Son, 2021). Kokkotas (2017) argues that access to materials and resources is crucial for developing a positive attitude towards science and for enhancing students' engagement and interest in the subject. Son (2021) emphasizes the role of hands-on activities and laboratory experiments in facilitating understanding of abstract concepts and promoting interest in science.

In light of these challenges, some teachers have resorted to creative solutions to overcome the lack of resources. For example, one teacher highlighted the importance of teacher resourcefulness in teaching Physical Science.

“Dapat po ay maging resourceful talaga ang teacher, kapag resourceful po nagkakaroon po ng solusyon ang guro”, while another emphasized the need for hands-on teaching “Sa Physical Science kase ay dapat more on hands-on talaga”. Additionally, some teachers have tried to localize content and use locally available materials to teach Physical Science “Mahirap ituro ang Physical Science kapag walang materials. Pwede naman maglocalize kaso ay hindi naman lahat ay available”.

Both the teachers and students highlighted the challenge of limited resources and lack of materials in teaching and learning Physical Science in a rural context. This includes the difficulty of obtaining materials, the lack of equipment and sources of information, and the limitations of black and white instructional materials. According to a study by Adodo (2021), limited resources can affect the quality of science education in rural areas, leading to lower academic achievement.

Subtheme 1.2. Teaching delivery faced challenges in comprehending abstract concepts.

Another common theme is the difficulty of understanding abstract concepts in Physical Science. Both teachers and students mention the challenge of teaching and learning complex terminology, technical terms, and abstract concepts. This can be attributed to the lack of hands-on experience and the reliance on imagination-based teaching in some cases. One of the respondents uttered that

“Dahil sa ang concept ng Physical Science ay may mga konsepto na hindi madaling maintindihan , ang mga bata ay nangangailangan pa rin ng gabay ng guro”.

According to a study by Walker and Goh (2021), the use of visual aids and analogies can help students understand abstract concepts better.

The subtheme 1.2. focuses on the difficulty in understanding abstract concepts in rural physical science pedagogy. The initial codes that lead to this subtheme are "super abstract concepts," "difficulty of teaching abstract concepts to children," "reliance on intelligent students to understand," and "difficulty of understanding topics for teachers."

Research has shown that abstract concepts are often difficult to learn and understand for students (Gilmore et al., 2019). In rural areas, where there is a lack of resources and materials, teachers often have to rely on students' imagination to understand abstract concepts (Boyd & Sloat, 2019). This can pose a challenge for students who may not have a strong foundation in

the subject, as well as for teachers who may not have the necessary resources to effectively explain these concepts.

Furthermore, some studies have suggested that there may be a correlation between a lack of understanding of abstract concepts and poor academic performance in science (Cho & Kim, 2017). Therefore, it is important for teachers to use various teaching strategies, such as hands-on activities and visual aids, to help students better understand abstract concepts.

In summary, subtheme 1.2. highlights the challenge of teaching abstract concepts in rural physical science pedagogy, which can be attributed to limited resources, reliance on students' imagination, and difficulty in understanding for both students and teachers.

Subtheme 1.3. Teaching delivery emphasizing the significance of hands-on learning.

Both the teachers and students emphasized the importance of hands-on learning in Physical Science. They noted that this approach can enhance learning and help students understand difficult concepts. However, the lack of materials and equipment in rural areas makes it challenging to implement this approach. According to a study by Bester et al. (2021), hands-on activities can be effective in promoting student engagement and academic achievement in science education.

The initial codes that lead to the subtheme 1.3, "Importance of hands-on learning," include "Importance of hands-on approach," "Relevance of hands-on teaching in Physical Science," "Challenges in localization of materials," and "Difficulty of teaching concepts to children." Teacher Respondents uttered that

“Mahirap po talagang ituro ang Physics lalo na pagdating sa mga bagay na kailangan ng experiment, hindi naman po pwedeng ipapamagine nalang, dapat po sila ay may hands-on.”

Several studies have emphasized the significance of hands-on learning in science education. According to Akcay and Arslan (2018), hands-on activities encourage students' active participation in learning, facilitate development of inquiry skills, and promote conceptual understanding. Authors further noted that hands-on learning can be particularly beneficial in rural areas where students may lack exposure to scientific phenomena and experiences. Similarly, a study by Santoso and Asyhar (2018) found that hands-on learning could improve students' academic achievement and motivation towards science learning.

The challenges in localizing materials for hands-on learning in rural areas have been recognized by several researchers. For example, in their study on science education in rural schools, Kocakulah and Şahin-Kızıl (2018) found that the lack of materials and resources hindered hands-on learning. The authors suggested that teachers should adapt instructional practices to accommodate the local context and utilize available resources effectively. Similarly, Awofala and Okebukola (2020) pointed out the challenges of localizing science teaching in rural areas due to the scarcity of instructional materials and resources. The authors suggested that teachers should leverage the local environment and use low-cost materials to facilitate hands-on learning. Overall, these studies highlight the importance of hands-on learning in science education and the challenges in localizing materials for such learning in rural areas. Teachers in

rural areas need to be resourceful and adapt their instructional practices to the local context to promote effective hands-on learning.

Subtheme 1.4. Challenges in teaching and learning during the pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought additional challenges to teaching and learning Physical Science in a rural context. Students and teachers highlighted the difficulties of teaching and learning remotely, the lack of internet connectivity in some areas, and the impact of student numbers on teaching quality. According to a study by Özkan et al. (2021), the pandemic has led to significant disruptions in science education, highlighting the need for flexible and adaptive teaching approaches. The statement

“Kaso nga lang po ay pagdating na po ng grade 12 ay nalilimutan na po nila iyong mga basic concepts na pinag aaralan sa science. May mga concept po sila na nalilimutan lalo’t dumaan po sila sa dalawang taong pandemic”

related to Subtheme 1.4. Challenges in teaching and learning during the pandemic include "pandemic, numbers, basic, lesson, and students." The codes suggest that COVID-19 pandemic has posed significant challenges for teaching and learning, particularly in the context of rural physical science pedagogy.

One major challenge has been the transition to online and remote learning, which has required significant adjustments for both teachers and students. As a result, many students have struggled with basic lessons and concepts, particularly those related to STEM subjects such as physical science (Chen, 2021).

Another challenge has been the difficulty in engaging students during remote learning, which can lead to a lack of motivation and interest in the subject matter. This can be particularly challenging in the context of physical science, which often requires hands-on learning and experimentation (Hu, Li, & Wu, 2021).

Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for flexibility and adaptability in rural physical science pedagogy, as well as the importance of finding innovative ways to engage students and maintain their interest and motivation in the subject matter.

Subtheme 1.5. Teaching delivery showcasing the resourcefulness and effectiveness of teachers.

Both teachers and students noted the importance of teacher resourcefulness and effectiveness in teaching and learning Physical Science. Teachers need to be creative and adaptable in their teaching methods to address the challenges of limited resources and materials. According to a study by Reuven and Cohen (2021), effective teaching methods should be student-centered, promote active learning, and be adapted to the specific needs and contexts of the learners.

The subtheme of teacher resourcefulness and effectiveness emerged from the initial codes related to the challenges faced by teachers in rural areas with limited resources and materials. Teachers need to rely on their resourcefulness and skills to effectively teach Physical Science to their students. The subtheme highlights the significance of instructional materials. One of the respondents stated that

“Nahihirapan po talaga sko sir, kaya nagloloocalize nalang po ako” which highlights the need for teachers to create their own instructional materials and resources to compensate for

the lack of commercially available materials in rural areas.

According to a study by Mabogoane and Mosimege (2020), teachers in rural areas need to be creative and resourceful to overcome the lack of materials and resources in their teaching of science subjects. Another statement related to this subtheme is

"Napakahalaga sir na resourceful ang teacher lalo na kapag nalilimutan nila ang basic concept ". Teachers in rural areas need to be familiar with the local context and culture to effectively teach Physical Science to their students.

According to a study by Chikasanda, Majawa, and Kaphuka (2016), teachers in rural areas need to adapt their teaching strategies and methods to the local context to make the subject more relevant and interesting to their students.

All of the initial codes from the five subthemes discussed earlier were integral in the following concept map.

Figure 2. The Rural Science Pedagogy 1 (RPSP1)

The concept map in Figure 2 that emerges from the responses is consistent with previous studies that have explored the teaching and learning science in a rural context. For example, a study by Bell et al. (2017) found that rural science teachers face significant challenges related to limited resources, including a lack of funding for equipment and technology, and limited access to professional development opportunities. Similarly, another study by Peters-Burton et al. (2016) found that rural students often have limited exposure to science and face challenges related to accessing the high-quality science instruction and resources.

Despite these situations, the responses suggest that both teachers and students are committed to engaging with science and recognize its importance for their future success. This aligns with the findings of a study by Czerniak et al. (2016), which found that rural students who were more engaged with science were more likely to pursue science-related careers. The responses also emphasize the importance of hands-on learning and guided instruction, which is

consistent with research on effective science teaching practices (National Research Council, 2012).

Finally, the responses highlight the importance of teacher resourcefulness and adaptability, particularly in the face of pandemic-related disruptions. This is consistent with recent research on the challenges faced by teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic, which has highlighted the need for flexibility, creativity, and support for teachers to effectively adapt to new teaching environments (Chen et al., 2020; UNESCO, 2020).

Theme 2: Rural Physical Science Pedagogy (RPSP2): Continuously Learning and Improvement on Physics and Chemistry Fundamentals

Upon analyzing responses from both the teachers and students, several subthemes emerge related to the teaching and learning of Physical Science in a rural context connected to teaching and learning of physics and chemistry fundamentals (RPSP2). The following are some of the themes that emerged from the coding of responses:

Subtheme 2.1. Success and Failure in teaching and learning of the fundamental principles and concepts

Success of Rural Science Pedagogy. The following are the identified success of rural science pedagogy based from the responses: (1) Teachers described certain concepts as successful in their responses, indicating that these concepts were effectively taught and understood by the students; (2) Teachers recognized successful teaching practices and strategies that facilitated student learning and engagement. (3) Student responses indicated successful learning experiences, where they felt confident and knowledgeable in the subject matter; (4) Factors contributing to success in rural science pedagogy included positive teacher-student interaction, high student interest, as well as effective English language proficiency.

Failure of Rural Science Pedagogy. On the other hand, the following are the statements categorized as failure of rural science pedagogy: (1) Teachers mentioned concepts that were not successful, suggesting that there were challenges in effectively teaching these topics to the students; (2) Teachers expressed difficulty in explaining certain concepts to the students, indicating a failure to communicate complex ideas effectively; (3) Student responses revealed instances of unsuccessful learning experiences, where they faced challenges or struggled to understand the subject matter, (4) Factors contributing to failure in rural science pedagogy included language barriers, lack of student interest, and low aptitude or understanding of the subject.

It becomes clearer that success and failure coexist in the context of rural science pedagogy. Both teachers and students have experiences that fall into each category, and multiple factors influence the outcomes. This separation allows for a more comprehensive analysis of the challenges and successes in rural science education, facilitating targeted improvements and future success.

Both the teachers and students mentioned the concepts of success and failure in their responses. Teachers described some concepts as successful and others as not successful, while students assessed their learning as successful or unsuccessful. In addition, both groups

acknowledged that success or failure can be influenced by a variety of factors, such as teacher-student interaction, student interest, and English language proficiency.

Under this subtheme, both teachers and students described their experiences of success and failure related to teaching and learning. Teachers identified some concepts as successful and others as not successful, while students assessed their learning as successful or unsuccessful. Additionally, both groups acknowledged that success or failure can be influenced by a variety of factors, such as teacher-student interaction, student interest, and English language proficiency.

One teacher response related to the success and failure subtheme was: "Some concepts are successful, but not all". This statement highlights the fact that not every concept can be taught successfully, and that there are inherent challenges in teaching certain topics. Another teacher response that relates to this subtheme is: "Difficulty explaining concepts to children", which suggests that some teachers may struggle with effectively communicating complex ideas to their students.

Similarly, student responses also highlighted the theme of success and failure.

For example, one student response stated that they had "Ako po kase ay hirap talaga kapag ang ginagamit po sa pagtuturo ay English". This statement suggests that language barriers can impact a student's ability to learn and may contribute to feelings of failure or frustration. Another student response that relates to this subtheme is: "Reason for success/failure: mahina po ako at hindi interisado sa Physics". This statement highlights the fact that student interest and aptitude can play a significant role in determining success or failure in a particular subject.

Overall, the subtheme of success and failure underscores the fact that learning is not always a linear process, and that both teachers and students may encounter challenges or obstacles along the way. By recognizing the potential for both success and failure, however, teachers and students can work together to identify areas for improvement and strive towards greater success in the future.

Subtheme 2.2. Teaching and Learning of the Basics

Teachers primarily focused on their experiences with teaching various basic concepts in physics and chemistry, while students primarily discussed their experiences with learning those concepts. However, both groups expressed a desire for effective teaching and learning, and identified factors that can facilitate or hinder these processes. These factors included the teacher's ability to explain concepts clearly, the student's level of engagement, and the relevance of the topic to the student's environment.

This subtheme relates to the experiences and perspectives of both teachers and students in the process of teaching and learning. Teachers described their approaches to teaching and the challenges they faced in conveying complex concepts to their students. Students, on the other hand, described their experiences of learning and the factors that helped or hindered their progress.

One teacher response that is related to this subtheme is "Successful in teaching fundamental principles in Physics and Chemistry".

This statement suggests that teachers may have specific areas of expertise, and that success in teaching may be contingent upon focusing on these areas.

Another teacher response that relates to this subtheme is "Positive view on success in teaching", which suggests that teachers who maintain a positive attitude towards teaching may be more successful in engaging and inspiring their students.

Student responses that relate to this subtheme include "Successful, Learning", and "Successful, Understanding, Unfinished Topics". They uttered that " Successful naman po sir naiintindihan naman po namin iyong mga naituro ni sir iyon nga lang po may mga hindi na po kami natapos nap ag-aralan".

These statements suggest that students may be more likely to succeed when they are able to learn and understand concepts, even if they have not yet fully mastered them. Additionally, one student response highlighted importance of teacher-student interaction, stating that they experienced "successful, good explanation, teacher-student interaction". One potential approach to fostering successful teaching and learning of fundamental concepts is through the application of social cognitive theory (Schunk & Usher, 2019), which emphasizes the importance of motivation and self-regulation in the learning process.

The subtheme of teaching and learning underscores the fact that effective teaching of fundamentals is a complex and multifaceted process, and that success in learning the basics is often dependent on a variety of factors. By recognizing the importance of teacher expertise, positive attitudes towards teaching, and effective teacher-student interaction, educators can help to facilitate more successful learning outcomes for their students.

Subtheme 2.3. Ongoing Learning

Both teachers and students acknowledged that learning is an ongoing process that requires continued effort and attention. Teachers described their own need for further research and improvement in their teaching, while students identified topics that they had not fully understood or areas where they needed more practice. In addition, both groups recognized that learning could occur in a variety of ways, such as through teacher-led instruction, student self-assessment, or identifying learning gaps.

The subtheme of ongoing learning highlights the idea that learning is a continuous process that extends beyond the classroom. Teachers and students alike described their experiences of ongoing learning, including their recognition of the need for further study and the identification of gaps in their knowledge.

One teacher response that is related to this subtheme is "Difficulty explaining concepts to children". This statement suggests that teachers may need to engage in ongoing learning to improve their teaching skills, particularly in terms of adapting to the needs and abilities of their students. Another teacher response that relates to ongoing learning is "need for research", which highlights the importance of ongoing learning in the context of scientific inquiry and discovery.

Student responses that relate to ongoing learning include "Acknowledgment of learning: learned from what was studied" and "Identification of learning gaps: there are still things to learn". These statements suggest that students recognize the value of ongoing learning and the fact that there is always more to learn, even after completing a course or program of study.

The subtheme of ongoing learning emphasizes the importance of recognizing that learning is a lifelong process, and that teachers and students alike can benefit from ongoing

efforts to expand their knowledge and skills. By acknowledging the need for ongoing learning and committing to ongoing personal and professional development, individuals can continue to grow and succeed in their chosen fields.

All of the initial codes from the five subthemes discussed earlier were integral in the following concept map.

Figure 3. Rural Science Pedagogy 2 (RPSP2)

After analyzing the subthemes that emerged from the initial responses/codes of both the teachers and students, the overarching theme that can be identified is the continuous process of learning and improvement.

Both groups recognized that learning is not a one-time event, but a continual process that involves ongoing effort, self-assessment, and identification of learning gaps. Furthermore, both groups acknowledged the importance of effective teaching and learning, and the role of various factors such as teacher-student interaction, student interest, and relevance of the topic in facilitating or hindering this process. Finally, both groups also acknowledged the possibility of success or failure, and recognized that success can be achieved through continued effort and improvement. Cox and Sanchez (2016) discussed the importance of ongoing education and training for developing global leaders. The authors emphasize the need for individuals to continuously learn and develop their skills, and note that this process involves not only formal education, but also informal learning experiences and personal reflection.

Thus, the overarching theme that can be derived from the subthemes is the continuous process of learning, growth, and improvement, in which teachers and students work together to achieve their goals and overcome any obstacles that may arise.

Theme 3: Rural Physical Science Pedagogy (RPSP3): Balancing Resource Constraints

and Effective Learning Strategies for Enhancing Student Learning

Upon analyzing the responses from both the teachers and students, several subthemes emerge related to the teaching and learning of Physical Science in a rural context pertaining to strategies and use of resources (RPSP3). The following are some of the subthemes that emerged from the coding of responses:

Subtheme 3.1. Teaching delivery constrained by insufficient resources for hands-on

The first emergent subtheme of "Lack of Resources for Hands-On Learning" highlights the importance of overcoming the challenges posed by a lack of laboratory equipment, materials, and time. Teachers reported difficulties in conducting experiments due to missing equipment and a lack of clarity on equipment usage in modules. Meanwhile, students reported infrequent opportunities to conduct experiments, limited experiment opportunities, and a lack of laboratory activities. However, despite these challenges, students and teachers reported strategies to maximize available resources, such as improvising materials and partnering with students to overcome resource constraints.

This subtheme relates to the need for adequate resources and equipment to facilitate effective STEM education.

This is highlighted by the statement “Napakadalang po naming mag experiment, hindi po namin ito nagagawa dahil po sa kakulangan sa equipment”.

As noted in the citation by Herrington and Parker (2021), resource-constrained STEM learning environments can present significant challenges to educators, who may struggle to provide students with access to hands-on learning opportunities. Without sufficient resources, students may be unable to engage in the kinds of experiments and activities that are essential to developing a deep understanding of STEM concepts.

Subtheme 3.2. Instructional delivery highlighting the significance of collaborative and multimedia learning.

The second emergent subtheme of "Importance of Collaborative and Multimedia Learning" emphasizes the role of collaborative learning, group work, and multimedia presentations in enhancing student learning. Students reported success in group work, simulations, and presentations, while teachers emphasized the importance of focusing on presentation and collaborative activities. Additionally, multimedia learning, such as videos and multimedia presentations, was reported as successful by both teachers and students.

Students and Teacher respondents stated that “Successful po sa group work, simulation at presentation”, it is supported by the teacher respondent that “Nagagawa po video video at presentation experiment lang po ang hindi”.

As noted by Bakia et al. (2012), online teacher professional development programs can be a powerful tool for improving STEM education outcomes by providing educators with the skills and knowledge they need to create engaging and effective multimedia learning experiences. Collaborative learning activities, such as group work and discussion, can also be highly effective in helping students build a deep understanding of STEM concepts

Subtheme 3.3. Teaching Method facing challenges in conducting experiments.

The third emergent subtheme of "Challenges with Conducting Experiments" encompasses the challenges students face with conducting experiments, such as limited experiment opportunities and unsuccessful performance in experiments. Teachers reported issues with conducting experiments, such as difficulty in conducting experiments due to missing equipment. However, despite challenges with conducting experiments, students still identified a learning gap in the lack of experimental learning and reported success in making videos and simulations.

This subtheme highlights the challenges that educators may face when attempting to conduct experiments in STEM classrooms.

Respondent uttered that "Hindi po kami nag-i-experiment sa Physical Science, dahil kulang kami sa tools at kulang din po sa oras".

As noted in the citation by Hmelo-Silver (2012), scaffolding technology-enhanced learning environments can be an effective strategy for helping students overcome these challenges by providing them with the guidance and support they need to engage in hands-on learning activities. However, these efforts may be hampered by a lack of resources, equipment, and time, as noted in the other citations.

To balance the limitations of resources with effective learning, teachers can employ a variety of strategies such as collaborative and multimedia learning and improvising materials. For instance, teachers can use multimedia presentations to supplement the lack of hands-on learning and engage students in the learning process. Additionally, teachers can partner with students to improvise materials and conduct experiments using available resources.

After coding and decoding all responses, the following concept map was generated and labeled as Rural Physical Science Pedagogy 3(RPSP3).

Figure 3. Rural Physical Science Pedagogy 3(RPSP3)

Figure 3 shows the overarching RPSP3 of "Balancing Resource Constraints and Effective Learning Strategies for Enhancing Student Learning" highlights the challenges faced by students and teachers when it comes to hands-on learning in resource-constrained environments. This theme encompasses the need to balance the limitations of resources with the need for effective learning experiences that engage students and enhance their understanding of concepts.

The theme also underscores the need for innovative strategies to overcome resource constraints and enhance student learning. By employing a variety of approaches, teachers can create engaging and effective learning experiences that enable students to develop a deeper understanding of concepts.

Theme 4: Rural Physical Science Pedagogy (RPSP4): Lack of Inquiry-Based Learning

Subtheme 4.1 Teaching enriched by teacher support and interaction.

There are several codes related to this theme. Teachers who are approachable and encourage questions create a positive learning environment for students, as evidenced by the code.

"Sir is approachable for questions, sinasagot nya po ang aming tanong kapag meron po kaming hindi naiintindihan".

This highlights the importance of teachers who prioritize engaging and stimulating lessons to keep students interested in science. Teachers who prefer student-initiated questioning can foster a culture of curiosity and inquiry in the classroom, as noted in the code "Preference for student-initiated questioning".

This subtheme emphasizes the importance of teacher-student interaction and the need for an approachable and supportive teacher. The codes related to this subtheme indicate that the teacher should be available to answer questions and encourage students to ask questions and participate in discussions. The teacher should also provide explanations and support student-initiated questioning. According to Bao et al. (2021), teacher-student interaction and communication are essential for creating a positive inquiry-based learning environment.

Subtheme 4.2 Education hindered by lack of hands-on exploration and experimentation.

There are also several codes put under this theme. Respondent stated that

"hindi nga lang po kami palaging nabibigyan ng time sa self-discovery, dahil wala pong internet".

The lack of hands-on exploration and experimentation in science education, as noted in the code "No experiments or exploration", can limit students' understanding of scientific concepts. The code "Not given time for self-discovery due to lack of internet access" highlights the challenges that students face in engaging in self-directed learning when resources are limited. Without access to laboratory facilities, as noted in the code "No laboratory use", students may miss out on important opportunities to engage in hands-on experimentation.

This subtheme highlights the limitations of a lack of hands-on exploration and experimentation in the learning process. The codes related to this subtheme indicate that the

absence of experiments or exploration due to limited facilities or lack of internet access can hinder students' learning experiences. Without laboratory use or discovery activities, students may struggle to fully understand and retain information. According to Akpan et al. (2020), hands-on experimentation in science education is essential for improving the students' critical thinking skills and promoting their deeper understanding of the scientific concepts.

Subtheme 4.3 Teaching with Limitations and Challenges of Inquiry

Several codes are seen connected to this theme. Students in rural areas may face gaps in their science education due to resource limitations and other factors, as noted in the code "Gaps due to being in a rural area". The code "Concern over lack of student questioning" highlights the need to encourage students to ask questions and engage in independent inquiry to deepen their understanding of the scientific concepts. Respondent uttered that

"Bihira lang po sir, dahil wala nga po kaming mapagkuhanan ng sagot dahil nga po nasa rural area po kami."

Teachers who struggle with large class sizes, as noted in the code "Difficulty with large class sizes", may face additional challenges in providing individualized attention and support to each student. The respondent uttered that

"Hindi lang po naming napi-perform ang handson activities. Dahil nga po siguro ang dami po namin sa isang klase. Nahihirapan din po siguro si sir na bantayan o kami isa isa."

This subtheme encompasses various limitations and challenges that affect the inquiry-based learning process, including the difficulty of large class sizes, the limitations of a rural area, and the lack of access to resources. The codes related to this subtheme indicate that the lack of facilities or resources can limit students' ability to ask questions, conduct research, or engage in discovery activities, hindering their understanding of the subject. As to Pritchard et al. (2021), inadequate resources and facilities in schools can negatively impact students' academic performance and lead to inequalities in education.

All of the responses were analyzed and decoded which led to the following concept map relating to RPSP4.

The overarching theme of the initial responses is the lack of inquiry-based learning in science education under the rural context.

Figure 5. Rural Physical Science Pedagogy 4 (RPSP4)

This theme is reflected in the subthemes of teacher support and interaction, lack of hands-on exploration and experimentation, and limitations and challenges in inquiry science education. Despite the importance of inquiry-based learning for developing critical thinking skills and deepening understanding of scientific concepts, many of the codes suggest that students are not being given enough opportunities for self-directed learning and exploration. Harlen et al. (2015), found that inquiry-based learning can improve students' understanding of scientific concepts and their attitudes towards science. The authors note that "inquiry-based learning enables learners to take control of their own learning, developing their own questions and hypotheses, designing and conducting their own investigations, and evaluating their own findings" (Harlen et al., 2015, p. 25). This aligns with the subtheme of teacher support and interaction, as teachers who encourage student-initiated questioning and provide individualized support can help facilitate inquiry-based learning.

Theme 5: Teachers & Students (RPSP5): Creating effective learning environments.

Upon the analysis of responses, the following subthemes emerged which relate to the teachers' role and how students learn science best in a rural setting.

Subtheme 5.1 Teaching Characterized by Active and hands-on learning

This subtheme highlights the importance of active and hands-on learning in the rural setting. Teachers should be flexible in their teaching approach, adjusting to the level and capacity of their students, and using varied strategies such as discovery learning and exploratory science to make learning enjoyable and effective. Additionally, teachers should provide adequate materials and laboratory activities to facilitate practical activities, experimentation, and faster

learning (Hands-on activities, Need for laboratory activities, Physical Science Laboratory facilities, Equipment).

Respondents uttered that “ *Kailangan po na ito ay ginagawa sa laboratory. Dapat po talaga ay facilitator lang po ang guro at naggaguide lang po sa bata mas matututo po sila kapag ganoon.*”

According to the research of Guo, Hao, and Su (2022), hands-on activities and experimentation are effective strategies to improve students' engagement, motivation, and achievement in science education.

Subtheme 5.2 Collaborative and learner-centered learning

This subtheme emphasizes the importance of creating a collaborative and learner-centered learning environment where students can discuss ideas, share their knowledge, and learn from each other. Teachers should encourage group study, discussion, and learner-centered activities to facilitate this type of learning (Discussion, Idea sharing, Group study, Learner-centered activities). Respondent stated that

“dapat po ang guro ay facilitator lang more on learner-centered po dapat ang mga activity”.

According to the research of Pan and Wong (2018), collaborative learning and learner-centered instruction are effective strategies to improve the students' academic achievement, problem-solving skills, and social interactions.

Subtheme 5.3 Teacher's role in facilitating learning.

This subtheme highlights the critical role of teachers in facilitating learning in the rural setting. Teachers should act as facilitators rather than traditional instructors, using a Q and A format and a facilitator role to encourage student participation and engagement (codes: facilitation vs. traditional teaching, Q and A format, Facilitator role). Additionally, teachers should provide guidance and avoid spoon-feeding among students to promote self-reliance and independence (teacher guidance, spoon-feeding among students). respondent stated that:

“Kung may laboratory po ay dapat facilitator lang po tayo”.

According to research of Ross and Bruce (2020), teacher facilitation and guidance are effective strategies to promote active and engaged learning in science education.

Subtheme 5.4 Importance of confidence and self-reliance

This subtheme highlights the importance of developing self-confidence and self-reliance in students in the rural setting. Teachers should encourage student confidence by avoiding a lack of confidence in students and promoting enjoyment of classes (Lack of confidence in students, Self-confidence, No reliance on others, Confidence in asking questions, Enjoyment of classes). Respondent stated that

“ Kailangan po ng tiwala sa sarili at dapat pong hindi ka dapat aasa sa iba”.

According to the research of Adelabu, Adu, and Adu (2019), building student confidence is a crucial factor in enhancing their learning outcomes and academic success.

All of the previous codes were taken into account which led to the development of the concept for RPSP5

Figure 5. Rural Physical Science Pedagogy 5(RPSP5)

Figure 5 shows RPSP5 which displays the overarching theme that emerged from the previous subthemes. The importance of creating effective learning environments that enable students to learn actively, collaborate with their peers, and develop their self-confidence and independence. Teachers play a critical role in facilitating this learning by using varied strategies, providing adequate materials, and encouraging experimentation and hands-on activities. Additionally, creating collaborative and learner-centered learning environment, where students are encouraged to ask questions and share ideas, is essential for effective learning. Ultimately, creating effective learning environments that meet the needs of students in rural areas is crucial for their success in their studies.

Theme 6: Learning KSA in Physical Science (RPSP6): Challenges and Opportunities in KSA Learning

The following subthemes emerged after analyzing the responses of teachers and students related to learning knowledge, skills, and attitudes (KSA) in senior high school.

Subtheme 6.1 KSA Learning Challenges

This subtheme relates to the difficulties that students and teachers face in the learning process. It includes codes which highlight the challenges of complex topics, lack of time and resources, incomplete learning, lack of interest, and confusion among students.

Respondent stated that:

“Medyo confusing po minsan, may mga topic po kase na masyadong malalim, mahirap po syang intindihiin muna. Minsan po ay kulang pa kami sa time bago po naming maiintindihan”.

The difficulty of understanding due to deep and complex topics (DCT) is a common challenge in the KSA learning (Acar & Uluyol, 2019). Moreover, inadequate time to comprehend (ITI) and insufficient resources necessitate further development (IRN) are also significant factors

that can hinder the learning process (Johnson, 2017). Students face difficulties in understanding complex topics, insufficient time, and lack of resources, which lead to incomplete learning and poor understanding. The teachers perceive the shallow understanding among the students, limitations in the rural context, lack of materials, and challenges in teaching complex science concepts.

Subtheme 6.2 Teaching Approaches and Strategies

This subtheme relates to the different approaches and strategies used by teachers to facilitate learning. It includes codes that highlight the importance of adequate explanations, knowledge sharing, experimentation, and hands-on activities to enhance understanding and skills. Teachers adjust their teaching level, use a gradual approach, and teach bit by bit to cater to the varying levels of understanding among students. Students learn from adequate explanations from their teacher, as well as from sharing and discussing ideas among classmates. Respondent stated that

“Kaya kailangan ko munang ituro ang basic talaga. Kaya po paunti-unti talaga”.

Effective teaching approaches and strategies are critical in KSA learning (Hakim, 2020). Gradual and bit-by-bit teaching approaches (TAA and TAA2) are effective in improving learning outcomes and retention (Lin, Chen, & Hung, 2021). Moreover, the development of understanding and the applicability of knowledge outside the classroom (DUA) is essential in motivating students and enhancing their skills (Mousoulides, 2019).

Subtheme 6.3 Knowledge and Skill Acquisition

This subtheme relates to the acquisition of knowledge and skills by students. It includes codes that highlight the importance of assessing students' knowledge foundation, identifying gaps in knowledge, and developing skills through gradual and systematic teaching. Students recognize their increased learning in Senior High School but note a rare opportunity for experimentation and insufficient development of knowledge, skills, and values. Respondent stated that

“Kailangan po munang ituro ang basic talaga, kaya lang ay paunti-unti talaga”.

Teachers note the need to teach the basics, develop understanding, and improve skills acquisition. Effective knowledge and skill acquisition is essential in KSA learning (Firmin & Karabenick, 2019). The assessment of student knowledge foundation (SKL) is an important step in identifying gaps and promoting learning (Brouwer & Korthagen, 2020). Moreover, the development of basic skills (TBS) and identification of incomplete knowledge and modules (INK, INM) help students acquire essential knowledge and skills.

Subtheme 6.4 External Factors Affecting Learning

This subtheme relates to external factors that affect the learning process. It includes codes that highlight the importance of addressing external factors such as limited resources, inadequate modules, and the effects of the pandemic on learning. Students note the effects of the pandemic on learning and the need for applicability outside of the classroom. Teachers

mention limitations due to the rural context, lack of internet access, and confusion with certain science concepts. They specified that

“ nalilimitahan sya dahil nga nasa rural context, kulang din ang allotted time para sa mga concept, tapos hindi naman pwedeng umasa lang sa modules. Minsan may mga topic din din akong hinahanap na wala sa module”.

External factors such as limited resources and the lack of materials can hinder the learning process (Nisha & Bhardwaj, 2019). Furthermore, the pandemic has had significant effects on KSA learning, such as increased online learning and limited access to resources (Mohammed, 2021). Therefore, addressing external factors is crucial in promoting effective KSA learning.

After analyzing and decoding all the previous responses, the following concept map is formed relating the learning of KSA in the senior high school. The overarching theme that emerges from the codes is the Challenges and Opportunities in KSA Learning and the need for improvement in the teaching and learning of knowledge, skills, and attitudes (KSA) in the Senior High School (SHS) level.

Figure 7. Rural Physical Science Pedagogy 6 (RPSP6)

Both students and teachers recognize the challenges and limitations faced in the classroom, such as insufficient time, resources, and understanding of complex topics. Teachers also note the need for adjustments in their teaching approaches and importance of developing students' knowledge and skills. Students emphasize the benefits of learning from adequate explanations, sharing and discussing ideas, and the importance of real-life application of their learnings. Finally, the effects of external circumstances, such as the pandemic and the rural context, are also noted as challenges to the teaching and learning of KSA in the SHS level.

It is important to address these challenges to ensure that students in the SHS level are equipped with the necessary KSA for their future careers and personal development. Teachers should be supported with adequate resources and training to improve their teaching approaches and ensure that students are able to acquire the knowledge and skills they need. Additionally,

incorporating more hands-on activities and real-life applications of concepts may also help students better understand and retain their learnings (Santos, Gardoce, & Mendoza, 2021).

Research Question Number 2: What are the factors that influence the success and failures of Physical Science Pedagogy in a rural context?

Theme 7: Factors Affecting Success and Failure of Science Pedagogy in a Rural Setting

After analyzing responses of students and teachers related to the factors affecting the success or failures of Physical Science Pedagogy in the rural setting, the following subthemes emerged.

Subtheme 7.1 Environmental and Resource Limitations

This subtheme includes lack of materials, equipment, and facilities for experiments, poor internet connectivity, and environmental challenges that hinder teaching and learning physical science.

Students specified that *“Wala pong internet at gadget maghihintay pa po kami ng kinabukasan para mgatanong sa guro”*. They also stated that *“Ganoon din po sir ang kakulangan sa facilities sir iyon din po ang dahilan kaya hindi po kami nakakapaglaboratory”*. Likewise another student justified that *“factor din po ang layo ng school sa bahay minsan po kase ay maputik at mahairap ang daan”*.

Teachers uttered that *“Unang una talaga ay materials, kasunod na ang equipment. May ilang equipment, kaso wala naman kaming mapaglagyan ng experiment. Ganoon din ang facility. Kase napakahirap na magkoconsume ka talaga ng ilang oras sa pagbibibit ng mga materials., ilang oras nalang ang natitira sa pagaactivity mo.*

According to Bravmann (2020), limited resources in rural areas are a challenge for educators. Lack of resources, inadequate facilities, and poor internet connectivity are common concerns in rural schools (Ahmed, 2020). Other codes connected to this subtheme are transportation issues, distance between home and school, and the condition of the road that makes it difficult for students to attend classes regularly.

The other related codes are lack of resources: Lack of materials, equipment, facilities, and resources for experiments and teaching physical science, as well as inadequate facilities, poor signal, and transportation issues.

Subtheme 7.2 Personal and Social Factors

This subtheme encompasses various personal and social factors such as household responsibilities, financial constraints, family problems, emotional issues, and external distractions that affect students' focus and concentration in learning physical science. Students stated that

“Wala po kami minsang pambili ng materyales na gagamitin sa activity”. Likewise another student added that *“Minsan po wala kaming baon ay malayo po ang bahay namin sa school. They also stated that “factor din po ang problema sa bahay. May mga gawaing bahay din. Ako din kasi ang nagbantay sa kapatid ko kaya po hindi ako nakakapasok”*.

Students who have to balance school and work, or who have family responsibilities, often

struggle with academic performance (Makara & Kosiba, 2019). Moreover, students' interest in the subject and their behavior also impact their academic performance. For Wang and Degol (2018), motivation, engagement, and persistence are critical components of student success in science. These related codes are Personal and social factors: Household responsibilities, financial constraints, family problems, emotional issues, and external distractions that affect students' focus and concentration, and students' interest in the subject and their behavior.

Subtheme 7.3 Pedagogical and Instructional Factors

This subtheme includes various pedagogical and instructional factors, such as teachers' capability to teach the subject, teaching style and strategy, language barrier, difficulty in understanding due to broad or insufficient explanation or shift in topics, overwhelming amount of concepts to learn, and lack of equipment and resources that hinder learning. Students stated that

“May mga mahihirap po talagang intindihing terms sa Physical Science, nararamdaman din po namin kung nahihirapan o ang guro namin na ituro ang isang subject.” This was resounded by teacher respondent who stated that “Hindi ako Science Major Sir, kaya minsan ay nahihirapan talaga ako sa mga terminologies.

Teachers uttered that *“Ganoon din ang comprehension and confidence ng guro. Ganoon din sa speaking skills ng guro. Kapag ang guro ay hirap sa pagdi-deliver ng concept kahit alam nya ang concept. Nahihirapan sya ay sa pag papaliwanang ng konsepto. Kapag ganoon ang nangyari hindi din ito maiintindihan ng bata. Ganoon din po, hindi ako sir Science Major talaga. Nahihirapan po ako sa mga terminologies.”*

Respondent justified that “Teachers' ability to deliver engaging and meaningful instruction is critical to student success in science (Hennessy & Onguko, 2021). Students benefit from explicit instruction, scaffolding, and teacher-led discussions that support learning (Tas, Peker, & Arslan, 2020). The related codes are pedagogical and instructional factors: Teachers' capability to teach the subject, teaching style and strategy, language barrier, difficulty in understanding, and lack of equipment and resources that hinder learning, overwhelming amount of concepts to learn, and shift in topics.

Subtheme 7.4 Technology and Information Limitations

This subtheme includes limited access to information and technology, such as the lack of gadgets and internet access, vocabulary related to the internet and signal, and the need for internet connectivity for online classes and research.

Student specified that *“Signal din po sir, minsan po ay kaakibat talaga ng science ang technology. Sa mga libro po ay may nakalagay na link ay dahil nga po walang signal, hindi po nagagwa ng bata ang mga activity. Pagdating ng teacher sa signal dun palang naming madadownload at saka ipapakita sa bata. Syempre po ang location kung nasaan ang school, pag ganito pong malayo ay bukod po sa may mga kulang sa gamit ay wala po talagang signal kaya kailangan po talagang mag strategize ang guro.”*

Teachers stated that *“factor din po ang kawalan ng kompletong gadget, ganoon din po ang kawalan ng Internet at Signal minsan po ay kaakibat talaga ng science ang technology. Sa mga libro po ay may nakalagay na link ay dahil nga po walang signal, hindi po nagagwa ng bata ang mga activity. Pagdating ng teacher sa signal dun palang naming madadownload at saka*

ipapakita sa bata. Syempre po ang location kung nasaan ang school, pag ganito pong malayo ay bukod po sa may mga kulang sa gamit ay wala po talagang signal kaya kailangan po talagang mag strategize ang guro.”

According to Marak and Gogoi (2019), technology infrastructure in rural areas is inadequate, resulting in limited access to information and technology. Additionally, students need internet connectivity for online classes and research (Jhala, Patel, & Patel, 2018). Lack of access to information and technology impacts student learning and achievement. The related codes are technology and information limitations: Limited access to information and technology, such as the lack of gadgets and internet access, vocabulary related to the internet and signal, and the need for internet connectivity for online classes and research.

After all the previous codes are decoded, the following concept map pertaining to factors affecting the success and failure of science pedagogy was developed.

Figure 8 on the succeeding page shows the overarching theme, the factors affecting the success and failure of physical science pedagogy in the rural setting. This theme encompasses four subthemes: environmental and resource limitations, personal and social factors, pedagogical and instructional factors, and technology and information limitations.

In rural areas, providing quality science education can be challenging due to lack of resources and facilities for experiments, poor internet connectivity, and environmental challenges.

Figure 8. Factors affecting the Success and Failure of Physical Science Pedagogy

As noted by McEwan and Bull (2016), rural schools often struggle to provide students with the necessary resources and facilities to learn science, including laboratories, equipment, and supplies. This lack of resources can make it difficult for students to understand scientific concepts and apply them to real-world situations.

Personal and social factors can also impact the quality of science education in rural areas. For example, students may face household responsibilities, financial constraints, and family problems that can affect their ability to focus on their studies. Additionally, students' interest in

the subject and their behavior can impact their academic performance, as noted by Sujatha and Sasikala (2020).

Pedagogical and instructional factors also play a significant role in the quality of science education in rural areas. Teachers' capability to teach the subject, their teaching style and strategy, and the difficulty in understanding scientific concepts due to insufficient explanation or an overwhelming amount of information can all hinder students' learning. According to a study by Bao et al. (2021), improving teacher training and support in rural areas can lead to better science education outcomes for students.

Finally, limited access to technology and information can also pose a challenge to providing quality science education in rural areas. The lack of gadgets and internet access can hinder students' ability to conduct research and access online resources, as noted by Amutabi (2019). Additionally, students may struggle with vocabulary related to the internet and signal, making it difficult for them to navigate online resources.

Furthermore, the challenges in providing quality science education in rural areas are multifaceted and require a holistic approach to address. By addressing the subthemes of environmental and resource limitations, personal and social factors, pedagogical and instructional factors, and technology and information limitations, educators and policy-makers can work towards improving science education outcomes for rural students.

Research Question Number 3: How do teachers and students retain success and overcome failures in Physical Science Pedagogy in a rural context?

Theme 8: Challenges and Coping Mechanisms in Teaching and Learning Physical Science in the Rural Setting

Subtheme 8.1 Coping Strategies of Students

This subtheme revolves around the different methods that students use to cope with the difficulties they encounter in learning Physical Science. These methods include borrowing books and requesting tutorial sessions, asking classmates and teachers for help, and searching for alternative research methods. Other strategies include requesting hands-on activities, additional video presentations and simulations, and computation lessons. This is justified in the statement of the respondent that “*Nanghihiram po kami ng libro sa teacher, humihingi rin po ako ng tulong sa kaibigan, family ko po at sa guro*”.

For example, in a study by Boado, et al. (2021), students coping mechanisms in learning Physical Science were explored, and it was found that many students cope by asking questions when they don't understand, hoping to revisit lessons from Junior High School, and focusing on studying Physical Science.

The following are some example codes under this subtheme: Borrowing books from teacher, asking questions when don't understand, hoping to revisit lessons from Junior High School, want to review topics that weren't understood, focusing on studying Physical Science, requesting materials for experiments and activities, asking for help from friend, family, and teacher, requesting tutorial in Physical Science, suggesting to split costs for experiment materials, searching for alternatives to materials, asking for help from relatives in town or with strong signal, and asking classmates or teachers for help when absent.

Subtheme 8.2 Teacher's Coping Strategies

This subtheme focuses on the different strategies employed by teachers to overcome the challenges of teaching Physical Science. These strategies include researching to solve difficult concepts, finding relevant and accessible resources, and being adaptive to different learners. Other strategies include providing handouts, searching for a resource speaker, and localizing with available resources.

Teacher respondent stated that “Lagi po akong nag ririsearch at nonood po ng mga video at tutorials”. Another teacher stated that “ang ginagawa ko po ay nagbibigay ako ng handouts, maliban sa mga modules nila, ako nalang ang naghahanap ng ibang references”. Another teacher justified that “Huwag tayong mahiyang magtanong dapat maging adaptive tayo sa ibat-ibang uri ng learners kaya naghahanap ako ng resource speaker para magdiscuss ng isang topic”.

In the study conducted by Vargas et al. (2021), the researchers examined the coping mechanisms employed by teachers when teaching Physical Science in rural settings. The findings revealed that teachers adopted various coping strategies to address the challenges they faced in these contexts. Some of the coping strategies identified included adapting teaching strategies, seeking assistance from colleagues, and resourcefulness in finding alternative teaching materials.

One of the coping mechanisms employed by teachers was the adaptation of teaching strategies. In rural settings, teachers recognized the diverse needs of their students and modified their instructional approaches accordingly. They adjusted their teaching methods to accommodate different learning styles and cater to the unique requirements of students in the context of Physical Science. This adaptability allowed teachers to enhance student engagement and comprehension. Another coping strategy involved seeking help from colleagues. Recognizing limitations and difficulties they encountered in teaching Physical Science, teachers actively sought assistance and support from their fellow educators. The collaborative efforts were crucial in sharing experiences, knowledge, and effective instructional practices. By engaging in professional networks, teachers were able to overcome challenges more effectively and improve their teaching outcomes.

Resourcefulness played a significant role in teachers' coping mechanisms. In the absence of readily available instructional materials, equipment, and facilities, teachers in rural settings demonstrated creativity and resourcefulness in finding alternative solutions. They actively sought out supplementary teaching materials and adapted existing resources to suit their teaching needs. This resourcefulness allowed teachers to provide quality education despite limited resources, enhancing the learning experience of their students.

The example codes provided in this subtheme further illustrate the specific coping strategies employed by teachers. Instructional materials, equipment, facilities, and schedule highlight the importance of adapting and improvising with available resources to create an effective learning environment. Perception, interest, readiness, and self-study emphasize the teachers' focus on understanding their students' individual needs and tailoring their teaching approaches accordingly. The mention of Physical Science and rural context emphasizes the specific challenges faced by teachers in teaching this subject in rural areas. Lastly, researching to ensure understanding, watching video tutorials, and reviewing lessons demonstrate the teachers' proactive approach in enhancing their own knowledge and skills to meet the demands of teaching Physical Science in rural settings.

Subtheme 8.3 Access to resources

This subtheme encompasses codes related to the availability and adequacy of instructional materials, equipment, and facilities needed for effective teaching and learning of Physical Science. Teachers and students alike encountered challenges in accessing these resources, which in turn affected their teaching and learning experiences. Teachers had to be resourceful and creative in adapting to limitations of their school's available resources, such as borrowing materials, searching for alternative research methods, localizing with available resources, and providing handouts.

Students requested additional books and equipment, hands-on activities, reduction in number of subjects per day, laboratory access, and a proper library. Student respondent stated that *"Nanghihiram po kami ng libro sa teacher sir at nagkukusa nalang po kami minsan humanap ng signal para makapag internet po, sana nga rin po ay mabigyan kami ng materials na pwede po naming gamitin sa experiment"*. Another student uttered that *"sana po ay may laboratory kami, model at equipment sa Physical Science"*.

These requests highlight the need for adequate resources to be made available to facilitate the teaching and learning of Physical Science in rural areas. According to Hughes and Quinn (2013), access to instructional materials and facilities is crucial in enhancing the quality of education. This subtheme encompasses codes such as instructional materials, equipment, facilities, handouts, and laboratory access.

Subtheme 8.4 Student Engagement

Student engagement encompasses codes related to the factors that affect student interest in learning Physical Science. Students encountered challenges such as financial difficulties, difficulty accessing the internet, sleepy students during afternoon classes, insufficient materials, and poor signal.

Teacher Respondent mentioned that *"Nagkakaroon po kami ng problema sa kakulangan ng pasilidad at mahinang internet kaya nagiging maparaan ako sa paggamit kung ano lang ang available"* This is supported by the statement *"To address these challenges, teachers employed various strategies such as finding ways to get children's attention, being adaptive to different learners, addressing students' needs, and finding relevant and accessible resources. The teacher respondent also stated that "kapag may kakulangan nag-aadjust ako sa bata"*.

On the other hand, students requested hands-on activities, reduction in the number of subjects per day, more engaging the teaching of Physical Science, additional video presentations and simulations, and computation lessons. These codes highlight the need for teachers to use engaging teaching strategies and to address the needs of their students to enhance their interest in learning Physical Science.

According to Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2004), student engagement is critical in promoting the student learning and academic achievement. This subtheme encompasses codes like student interest, engagement, teaching strategies, and addressing students' needs.

All the previous codes were decoded which paved way to the development of the following concept map connected to the challenges and coping mechanisms in the teaching and learning of physical science in the rural setting.

Figure 9. Challenges and Coping Mechanisms in Teaching and Learning Physical Science in the Rural Setting

Figure 9 shows the overarching theme, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms in Teaching and Learning Physical Science in the Rural Setting. The codes related to the challenges highlight the difficulties encountered in teaching and learning Physical Science in rural areas, such as limited access to instructional materials, equipment, and facilities, as well as the factors that affect student interest in learning. On the other hand, the codes related to coping mechanisms highlight the strategies employed by teachers and students to overcome these challenges, such as being resourceful, seeking help, and adapting to different learners.

The overarching theme emphasizes the importance of being adaptive and creative in addressing the challenges encountered in teaching and learning Physical Science in rural areas. This theme highlights the unique difficulties that teachers and students face in the rural context and the strategies they use to overcome these challenges.

Teaching and learning physical science in a rural setting is a complex process that involves various factors such as limited access to instructional materials and equipment, inadequate facilities, and unfamiliarity with scientific terminologies. These challenges may affect the students' interest and motivation to learn, as well as the teacher's ability to effectively deliver the lessons.

However, both the teachers and the students employ various coping mechanisms to overcome these challenges. Teachers adapt their teaching strategies and seek help from different sources such as resource speakers, websites, and other teachers from Junior High School. They also utilize available resources and find creative ways to provide hands-on activities and relevant samples to their students.

On the other hand, students cope with the challenges by seeking help from their teachers, classmates, and even their relatives. They also request for additional materials and equipment, as well as hands-on activities and laboratory access to enhance their understanding and retention of the lessons.

The theme emphasizes the importance of resourcefulness, adaptability, and collaboration in teaching and learning physical science in a rural setting. It also underscores the need for better facilities, equipment, and materials, as well as engaging teaching strategies that cater to the unique needs and interests of the students.

OBJECTIVE 4: Design a Learning Action Cell Plan that can be used to address the challenges of Science Teachers in rural area

Theme 9. Importance of improving teaching strategies and resources in Physical Science

After analyzing the responses in relation to the suggestion for learning action cells, the following emergent subthemes were identified:

Subtheme 9.1 Training and strategies for teaching Physical Science

One of the identified subtheme or subcategories is the need for training and strategies for teaching Physical Science. Many of the teachers recognize the importance of constantly improving and innovating teaching strategies to make difficult topics more accessible to students.

Teacher respondent stated that “*Sa tingin ko training o strategies kung paano ituturo ang pagtuturo ng Physical Science, Sana magkaroon tayo ng training.*”

A study by Lavy and Sand (2015) found that professional development programs for science teachers had a positive impact on student learning outcomes. This highlights the importance of providing ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their teaching strategies and improve student achievement.

Some of the notable codes identified in this study are the: need for training on teaching strategies, innovative teaching methods, focus on science and strategies in training, strategy sharing. Teachers suggest a need for training on teaching strategies to improve their delivery of science lessons and propose innovative teaching methods to make science more engaging for students.

Subtheme 9.2 Compliance with MELC and Review of Physical Science topics

Another category or subtheme that emerged is the need for compliance with the MELC and review of Physical Science topics. Teachers recognize the importance of ensuring compliance with the curriculum guidelines to ensure students are receiving a comprehensive education. Additionally, reviewing Physical Science topics helps teachers identify areas where students may need more support.

Teacher respondent mentioned that “*Seminars po sana about topic po ng Physical Science na mababalikan po ang MELC.*”

A study by Mangubhai, Dashwood, and Annabell (2016) found that reviewing science content helped teachers identify misconceptions that their students held, and this led to improved student learning outcomes.

Some of the notable codes identified under this subtheme are the Physical Science improvement, review of Physical Science topics and MELC. Teachers suggest a need for improvement in physical science education, including the review of physical science topics and adherence to the MELC (Most Essential Learning Competencies).

Subtheme 9.3 Availability and familiarization with equipment and materials

The availability and familiarization with equipment and materials is another subtheme that emerged from the teachers' responses. Teachers recognize that access to adequate resources is important to ensure students are receiving a quality education.

Respondent stated that “*dapat sana sir kahit tayo ay nasa rural ay may laboratory at equipment pa rin ang bata*” Another teacher added that “*Ganoon din po sana ang mga materials ay ipakilala sana sa mga guro kapag idi-deliver sa amin sa school*”.

A study by Manu, Oteng-Pepurah, and Amedahe (2018) found that the availability of laboratory equipment had a positive impact on student motivation, engagement, and achievement. Additionally, teachers need to be familiar with the equipment and materials to ensure they can effectively integrate them into their lessons.

Some of the notable codes identified to be under this team are: Availability of TV in classrooms, introduction of materials to teachers, need for laboratory, familiarization with equipment, complete materials, facilities. Teachers suggest improvements to the availability of resources, including the introduction of materials to teachers, familiarization with equipment, and the need for laboratory facilities.

Subtheme 9.4 Specific topics in Physical Science

Another subtheme that emerged is the specific topics in Physical Science that teachers identified as being particularly difficult or important. Teachers mentioned difficult topics such as Stellar Nucleosynthesis, Polar and Non-Polar, and the Theory of Relativity.

Teacher respondent stated that “*sana po ay magkaroon ng training sa mahihirap na topic kagaya ng Stellar Nucleosynthesis, Polar and Non-Polar, and the Theory of Relativity*”.

Focusing on these specific topics allows teachers to better tailor their lessons to meet needs of their students. A study by Dancy and Henderson (2010) found that tailoring instruction to specific student needs led to improved student achievement in science.

The following are notable codes related to the said subtheme: Physical Science, Stellar Nucleosynthesis, Polar and Non-Polar, Theory of Relativity. Teachers suggest focusing on specific topics within physical science, including the challenging topics of Stellar Nucleosynthesis, Polar and Non-Polar, and Theory of Relativity.

Subtheme 9.5 Suggestions for improvement

The final subtheme that emerged is the suggestions for improvement that teachers provided. Teacher respondent uttered that “*Sana po ay magkaroon ng LAC about teaching techniques, specific topic in Physical Science at magkaroon ng TV ang lahat ng classroom para po mas Madali po sa guro ang pagtuturo na may kasamang presentation sir.*”

These suggestions included localized activities, inviting science majors as speakers, and conducting seminars on Physical Science topics. These suggestions can help teachers improve their lessons and engage students in learning. Additionally, suggestions such as complete materials, facilities, and availability of TV in classrooms can help improve the overall learning environment for students.

The notable codes for this subtheme are Suggested/localized activities, Inviting a science major as a speaker, and Laboratory demo during SLAC. All of the previous responses were decoded which led to the development of the following concept map, Importance of improving teaching strategies and resources in Physical Science.

Figure 10. Importance of improving teaching strategies and resources in Physical Science

Figure 10 shows the overarching theme and its connections to five themes related to suggestions for the action cell topics. The overarching theme that emerged from the subthemes is the importance of improving teaching strategies and resources in Physical Science. This includes training and strategies for teaching physical science, compliance with MELC and review of physical science topics, availability and familiarization with equipment and materials, specific topics in physical science and suggestions for improvement. These findings are consistent with previous research that highlights the importance of teacher professional development, access to resources, and tailoring instruction to student needs to improve student learning outcomes (Lavy & Sand, 2015; Manu et al., 2018; Dancy & Henderson, 2010).

Conclusions

From the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Rural science teachers encounter obstacles like limited resources, inadequate training, and low student interest, requiring customized training, resource provision, and engaging curricula to improve student learning outcomes.
2. Environmental and resource limitations, personal and social factors, pedagogical and instructional factors, and technology and information limitations impact the success and failure of rural physical science pedagogy, necessitating the establishment of a conducive learning

environment, adoption of student-centered teaching strategies, and utilization of suitable technology to enhance science education in rural areas.

3. The study emphasized the significance of adaptability and creativity in tackling challenges faced in rural Physical Science education, with coping mechanisms involving resourcefulness, seeking assistance, and adapting to diverse learners, and to enhance student learning outcomes, it is essential to offer support to teachers and students, foster peer learning opportunities, and encourage collaboration among stakeholders.

4. Enhancing student learning outcomes in physical science requires improving teaching strategies and resources, and the study developed a localized Learning Action Cell (LAC) plan that promotes collaboration among teachers, school administrators, and stakeholders to develop innovative teaching methods and utilize available resources, ultimately enhancing the quality of physical science education in rural areas. Implementing this plan enables teachers to achieve teaching breakthroughs and improve student learning outcomes in the subject.

Recommendations

From the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The school administration may increase support and funding for science education in rural areas to address the lack of resources, equipment, and facilities that impede effective teaching and learning.

2. The school district and its component schools may provide additional professional development opportunities for teachers in rural areas to enhance their pedagogical knowledge and skills, particularly in teaching physical science. This could include training on effective teaching strategies, innovative ways to teach physical science topics, and how to use available resources to enhance instruction.

3. The school may encourage collaboration among teachers, school administrators, and stakeholders in the rural setting to develop innovative teaching methods and leverage available resources to improve the overall quality of physical science education.

4. School district administrators and school heads may ensure that physical science curricula are designed and implemented in a way that is relevant and engaging to students in rural areas, taking into consideration the unique environmental and social factors that affect their learning.

5. School principals and science head teachers may encourage the use of technology and information resources to supplement physical science instruction, particularly in rural areas where access to physical resources and equipment may be limited.

6. School principals and science head teachers may establish learning action cells in rural schools to promote peer-to-peer learning and provide teachers with ongoing support and feedback. This will help teachers develop innovative teaching methods, share resources and ideas, and enhance the overall quality of physical science instruction in rural areas.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In preparation for the structured interviews, participants were not only requested to

provide informed consent but were also provided with a thorough explanation of the study's objectives. Explicit consent for recording the interviews was also diligently sought. Throughout the study, participants were consistently reminded of their right to withhold their thoughts on specific topics or decline to answer questions.

The researcher placed paramount importance on the security and confidentiality of the participants. All data collection and analysis procedures were meticulously carried out with an unwavering commitment to safeguarding the identity and privacy of the respondents. Rigorous steps were taken to ensure anonymity, providing an additional layer of protection for the participants.

Participants were not only informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any repercussions, but they were also assured of this absolute freedom. The researcher respected their right to discontinue participation without any questions asked, ensuring that their choices were honored throughout the study.

Furthermore, it is crucial to note that participants were never exposed to any form of harm during any phase of the research. The researcher took stringent measures to guarantee that the study did not cause any physical or psychological harm to the respondents.

This study was conducted with an unwavering commitment to a conflict-free environment. It was undertaken solely with the purpose of contributing to the body of knowledge and understanding in the field of study.

In addition to upholding ethical standards, strict measures were in place to prevent plagiarism. Every source and reference was accurately cited, and the research was conducted with academic integrity at its core.

The analysis of research findings was executed with a profound commitment to impartiality. The researcher ensured that findings were interpreted objectively, devoid of any preconceived notions, thus maintaining the integrity of the study.

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